

Effect of temperature on the partial molar volumes of some high valency electrolytes in water-rich region of binary aqueo-organic mixtures

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Abstract : Partial molar volumes of some high valency electrolytes viz. potassium ferrocyanide and potassium ferricyanide have been determined in aqueous and binary aqueo-organic mixtures of acetonitrile (ACN) and methanol (MeOH) in water-rich region [5, 10, 15, 20 and 25% by weight of ACN and MeOH] from solution density measurements at 303.15 K, and in water and 5% (w/w) ACN + H₂O and MeOH + H₂O at five equidistant temperatures [298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K]. The density data have been analysed by means of Masson's equation. The partial molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) and slopes (S_v^*) have been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions, respectively. The partial molar volumes vary with temperature as a power series of temperature. Structure making/breaking capacities of the high valency electrolytes have been inferred from the sign of $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$ i.e. the second derivative of partial molar volumes w.r.t. temperature at constant pressure. The high valency electrolytes behave like common electrolytes in water and like symmetrical tetra-alkyl ammonium salts in binary aqueo-organic mixtures. The high valency electrolytes act as structure breakers in water and structure makers in binary aqueo-organic mixtures. The behaviour of high valency electrolytes changes on the addition of organic solvent.

Keywords : High valency electrolytes, partial molar volumes, binary aqueo-organic mixtures.

Introduction

In continuation of our earlier studies¹⁻⁴, the aim of present study is to see the effect of the added organic solvents on the behaviour of high valency electrolytes when water is diluted by a polar protic (MeOH) solvent and dipolar aprotic (ACN) solvent.

Results and discussion

The densities measured for the solutions of high valency electrolytes viz. potassium ferrocyanide [$K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$] and potassium ferricyanide [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$] in water and organic solvent + water [5, 10, 15, 20 and 25% by weight of ACN or MeOH] at 303.15 K have been used to calculate the apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) of the electrolytes. The plots of ϕ_v against the square root of molar concentration ($c^{1/2}$) were found to be linear for both the high valency electrolytes in aqueous as well as in different compositions of aqueo-organic mixtures. The partial molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) were calculated using least square fits to the linear plots of experimental values of ϕ_v versus square root of molar concentration, c , using the following Masson relation⁵ :

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* c^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where $\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}_2^0$ is the partial molar volume and S_v^* the

experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* , along with standard errors, obtained in water and in different compositions of aqueo-organic solvents at 303.15 K are recorded in Table 1.

It is evident from Table 1 that the values of S_v^* become positive as the system changes from water to aqueous mixtures of ACN or MeOH at 303.15 K. Addition of small amount (5% w/w) of organic solvent (ACN/MeOH) to water changes the sign of S_v^* from negative in water to positive in ACN + water and MeOH + water. The positive values of S_v^* for potassium ferrocyanide and potassium ferricyanide in ACN + water and MeOH + water mixtures at 303.15 K suggest the presence of strong ion-ion interactions, which further decrease with the increase in composition of ACN or MeOH in water thereby showing that ion-ion interactions are weakened with the increase of organic solvent, which may be attributed to the increase in solvation of ions.

It is also clear from Table 1 that the values of ϕ_v^0 are positive and large for both the high valency electrolytes in water as well as in aqueo-organic mixtures at 303.15 K, thereby showing the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions, which are further strengthened on the addition of organic solvent to water.

Table 1. Partial molar volumes (ϕ_v^0), experimental slopes (S_v^*) and partial molar volumes of transfer ($\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$) for potassium ferrocyanide and potassium ferricyanide in water, in different compositions of ACN + water and MeOH + water at 303.15 K
Standard errors are given in parentheses

Composition of ACN/MeOH+ water (wt%)	$\phi_v^0 \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$S_v^* \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^3 \text{ dm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-3/2}$)	$\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0 \times 10^{-6}$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
ACN + water			
Potassium ferrocyanide :			
0 (water)	217.79 (± 0.22)	-243.03 (± 1.80)	-
5	156.67 (± 0.05)	72.27 (± 0.42)	-61.12
10	158.93 (± 0.05)	68.42 (± 0.39)	-58.86
15	163.00 (± 0.03)	64.17 (± 0.28)	-54.79
20	165.88 (± 0.03)	58.75 (± 0.28)	-51.91
25	169.60 (± 0.02)	50.82 (± 0.19)	-48.19
Potassium ferricyanide :			
0 (water)	196.39 (± 0.08)	-169.34 (± 0.63)	-
5	96.86 (± 0.24)	262.74 (± 1.94)	-99.53
10	98.41 (± 0.17)	259.95 (± 1.38)	-97.98
15	100.65 (± 0.14)	258.42 (± 1.16)	-95.74
20	102.00 (± 0.29)	255.02 (± 2.37)	-94.39
25	104.55 (± 0.41)	253.01 (± 3.39)	-91.84
MeOH + water			
Potassium ferrocyanide :			
5	192.15 (± 0.02)	44.42 (± 0.13)	-25.64
10	195.98 (± 0.02)	42.02 (± 0.14)	-21.81
15	200.42 (± 0.02)	40.57 (± 0.21)	-17.37
20	204.26 (± 0.01)	36.48 (± 0.09)	-13.53
25	208.30 (± 0.02)	31.68 (± 0.14)	-9.49
Potassium ferricyanide :			
5	103.94 (± 0.15)	336.63 (± 1.21)	-92.45
10	106.30 (± 0.28)	334.77 (± 2.31)	-90.09
15	107.87 (± 0.22)	332.96 (± 1.79)	-88.52
20	110.48 (± 0.28)	329.04 (± 2.29)	-85.91
25	112.52 (± 0.12)	324.24 (± 1.04)	-83.87

The volumes of transfer ($\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$) have been calculated using the following expression :

$$\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0 = \phi_v^0(MS) - \phi_v^0(W) \quad (2)$$

These values are also recorded in Table 1. Here $\phi_v^0(MS)$ and $\phi_v^0(W)$ are the partial molar volumes of the individual electrolyte in the mixed solvent (ACN + water or MeOH + water) and water, respectively. The increase in ϕ_v^0 and $\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^0$ (in magnitude), for both the electrolytes may be attributed to the decrease in electrostriction effect in the presence of organic solvent. Thus the electrostriction effect, which brings about shrinkage in the volume of solvent, decreases with the increase of organic solvent in water.

Since the behaviour of the individual high valency electrolyte was found to be linear and identical in different compositions of binary aqueo-organic mixtures at 303.15 K therefore 5% (w/w) ACN + water and MeOH + water were selected for studying the effect of temperature. For the comparison of results, the effect of temperature on water was also studied. The densities were determined for both the high valency electrolytes in water and in 5% (w/w) ACN + water and MeOH + water at different temperatures [298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K]. The linear plots of ϕ_v versus $c^{1/2}$ have

been obtained at different temperatures for individual high valency electrolyte. The values of limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) and the experimental slopes (S_v^*) at different temperatures have been obtained by using least-square fits to the plots of ϕ_v versus $c^{1/2}$. These values, along with standard errors, are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Partial molar volumes (ϕ_v^0), experimental slopes (S_v^*) and partial molar volume expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) for high valency electrolytes in water and in 5% (w/w) ACN + water and MeOH + water at different temperatures
Standard errors are given in parentheses

Temp. (K)	$\phi_v^0 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$S_v^* \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$)		$\phi_E^0 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
		Water		
Potassium ferrocyanide :				
298.15	208.30 (± 0.19)	-217.40 (± 1.53)		1.600
303.15	217.79 (± 0.22)	-243.03 (± 1.80)		1.470
308.15	220.87 (± 0.34)	-247.20 (± 2.74)		1.340
313.15	229.38 (± 0.30)	-250.72 (± 2.46)		1.210
318.15	236.93 (± 0.30)	-269.53 (± 1.01)		1.080
Potassium ferricyanide :				
298.15	191.27 (± 0.06)	-162.74 (± 0.52)		1.263
303.15	196.39 (± 0.08)	-169.34 (± 0.63)		1.013
308.15	201.37 (± 0.05)	-178.23 (± 0.40)		0.763
313.15	204.01 (± 0.16)	-179.65 (± 1.33)		0.513
318.15	209.62 (± 0.09)	-180.48 (± 0.70)		0.263
5% (w/w) ACN + water				
Potassium ferrocyanide :				
298.15	152.76 (± 0.02)	78.73 (± 0.18)		0.581
303.15	156.67 (± 0.05)	72.27 (± 0.42)		0.621
308.15	160.96 (± 0.03)	67.76 (± 0.23)		0.661
313.15	165.30 (± 0.01)	48.95 (± 0.10)		0.701
318.15	168.17 (± 0.01)	46.94 (± 0.06)		0.741
Potassium ferricyanide :				
298.15	94.31 (± 0.22)	268.57 (± 1.82)		0.638
303.15	96.86 (± 0.24)	262.74 (± 1.94)		1.048
308.15	105.18 (± 0.35)	233.55 (± 2.90)		1.458
313.15	112.60 (± 0.22)	218.46 (± 1.80)		1.868
318.15	122.97 (± 0.10)	202.40 (± 0.80)		2.278
5% (w/w) MeOH + water				
Potassium ferrocyanide :				
298.15	187.41 (± 0.02)	52.39 (± 0.15)		0.308
303.15	192.15 (± 0.01)	44.42 (± 0.13)		0.558
308.15	195.08 (± 0.10)	37.90 (± 0.08)		0.808
313.15	202.42 (± 0.02)	30.13 (± 0.12)		1.059
318.15	205.67 (± 0.01)	27.29 (± 0.09)		1.309
Potassium ferricyanide :				
298.15	101.46 (± 0.11)	347.06 (± 0.92)		-0.496
303.15	103.94 (± 0.15)	336.63 (± 1.21)		0.604
308.15	109.10 (± 0.12)	315.17 (± 1.00)		1.704
313.15	113.94 (± 0.24)	301.55 (± 1.94)		2.804
318.15	130.08 (± 0.17)	237.69 (± 1.43)		3.904

Note

It is evident from Table 2 that the values of S_v^* are negative for both the high valency electrolytes in water at all temperatures, thereby suggesting the presence of weak ion-ion interactions, which are further weakened with rise in temperature. It is also clear from Table 2 that the values of S_v^* are positive for both the high valency electrolytes in binary aqueo-organic mixtures at all temperatures, thereby suggesting the presence of strong ion-ion interactions. From the values of S_v^* for potassium ferrocyanide and potassium ferricyanide it may also be concluded that ion-ion interactions are more stronger in case of potassium ferricyanide as compared to potassium ferrocyanide which implies that ferrocyanide ion $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ is more strongly solvated as compared to ferricyanide ion $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$.

The values of ϕ_v^0 are positive for both the high valency electrolytes in water as well as in 5% (w/w) binary aqueo-organic mixtures at all temperatures, suggesting the existence of strong ion-solvent interactions in both the systems (water, aqueo-mixtures). Further, the values of ϕ_v^0 increase with the increase of temperature for both the high valency electrolytes in water and binary aqueo-organic mixtures, which may be attributed to the increase in solvation of multi-charged ions with the rise in temperature.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 , in water and 5% (w/w) binary aqueo-organic mixtures can be expressed by the following expressions :

In water :

$$\phi_v^0 = -1422.75 (\pm 3.15) + 9.352 (\pm 1.500) T - 0.013 (\pm 0.003) T^2 \quad (3)$$

for potassium ferrocyanide, and

$$\phi_v^0 = -2406.38 (\pm 2.00) + 16.170 (\pm 0.210) T - 0.025 (\pm 0.001) T^2 \quad (4)$$

for potassium ferricyanide

In 5% (w/w) ACN + water :

$$\phi_v^0 = 306.87 (\pm 2.37) - 1.804 (0.002) T + 0.004 (\pm 0.001) T^2 \quad (5)$$

for potassium ferrocyanide, and

$$\phi_v^0 = 3548.63 (\pm 4.81) - 23.810 (\pm 4.030) T + 0.041 (\pm 0.007) T^2 \quad (6)$$

for potassium ferricyanide

In 5% (w/w) MeOH + water :

$$\phi_v^0 = 2220.27 (\pm 6.26) - 14.934 (\pm 0.088) T + 0.026 (\pm 0.002) T^2 \quad (7)$$

for potassium ferrocyanide, and

$$\phi_v^0 = 2064.22 (\pm 3.26) - 13.620 (\pm 0.011) T + 0.024 (\pm 0.004) T^2 \quad (8)$$

for potassium ferricyanide

T = absolute temperature

The partial molar volume expansibilities, $\phi_E^0 = [\partial\phi_v^0 / \partial T]_p$ calculated using expressions (3) to (8) for both the high valency electrolytes, in water and in 5% (w/w) aqueo-organic mixtures, have also been recorded in Table 2. It is evident from Table 2 that ϕ_E^0 decreases in magnitude with the increase in temperature for both the high valency electrolytes in water thereby indicating that the behaviour of high valency electrolytes is just like common electrolytes, because in case of common electrolytes the molar expansibilities should decrease with the increase in temperature⁶.

In case of binary aqueo-organic mixtures the value of ϕ_E^0 increases with the increase in temperature for both the high valency electrolytes thereby showing that these salts do not behave like common electrolytes, rather their behaviour is just like tetra-alkyl salts in binary aqueo-organic mixtures. In other words the behaviour of high valency electrolytes changes with the change of solvent from aqueous to aqueous-organic solvent.

The variation of ϕ_E^0 with temperature for both the high valency electrolytes is linear in water as well as in binary aqueo-organic mixtures. A sample plot for both the high valency electrolytes in 5% (w/w) ACN + water is shown in Fig. 1. The decrease in ϕ_E^0 in water may be ascribed to the absence of a "cageing effect". The positive increase in ϕ_E^0 in aqueo-organic mixtures may be ascribed to the presence of a "cageing effect"⁶. High valency electrolytes occupy the interstitial spaces in the binary aqueo-organic system resulting in structure making/hydrophobic character.

During the first few years, it has been emphasized by some workers that S_v^* is not the sole criterion for determining the structure making/breaking character of any solute. Hepler⁷ has developed a technique of examining

Fig. 1. Variation of ϕ_E^0 with temperature for potassium ferricyanide and potassium ferrocyanide in 5% acetonitrile + water.

the sign of $[\partial^2\phi_V^0/\partial T^2]_p$ for various solutes in term of long range structure making or breaking character of the solute in aqueous solutions using the following thermodynamic relation :

$$[\partial C_p/\partial P]_T = -[\partial^2\phi_V^0/\partial T^2]_p \quad (9)$$

On the basis of this relation, it has been deduced that structure maker solutes should have positive values whereas structure breaker solutes negative values. In the present study, it is observed from expressions (3) to (8) that the value of $[\partial^2\phi_V^0/\partial T^2]_p$ in water is negative while it is positive in 5% (w/w) aqueo-organic mixtures for both the high valency electrolytes, thereby showing that both the high valency electrolytes act as structure breakers in

water and structure makers/promoters in binary aqueo-organic mixtures. The behaviour of high valency electrolytes changes from structure breakers to structure makers when the solvent is changed from aqueous to binary aqueo-organic mixture. Addition of small quantity of organic solvent to water changes the behaviour of high valency electrolytes altogether.

Experimental

Potassium ferrocyanide $[\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and potassium ferricyanide $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ (A.R. s.d. fine chem.) were used for present study.

Acetonitrile and methanol (99% pure, E. Merck), af-

ter standing over anhydrous calcium oxide for about 48 h, were shaken vigorously with P_2O_5 and then distilled. The first and last fractions were discarded. The middle fractions were refluxed again over calcium oxide and refractionated to obtain acetonitrile and methanol for present study. The densities and viscosities for acetonitrile and methanol at 303.15 K were $0.77189 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $0.329 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N sec m}^{-2}$ (ACN), and $0.7817 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $0.511 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N sec m}^{-2}$ (MeOH), respectively. These values agree with literature values⁸.

The experimental procedure is exactly the same as described in our earlier communication^{9,10}. The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) were calculated from the density data by using the following standard expression¹¹:

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d_0} - \left[\frac{d - d_0}{d_0} \right] \frac{10^3}{c} \quad (10)$$

where d_0 is the solvent density, (water, binary aqueo-organic mixtures). The density measurements were carried out in a well-stirred water-bath whose temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$.

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